

Supplementary Information for:

Comparing the fate of eDNA by particle sizes and molecule lengths in recirculating streams

Number of pages: 8

Number of figures: 7

Figure S1: Pictures of Notre Dame Experimental Mesocosm Facility (ND-EMF). [A] All 24 artificial recirculating streams during experiment described herein. Note shade cloth over two groups of mesocosms. [B] Wide-eye lens picture of one mesocosm showing the mixture of substrates used for the experiment. [C] No substrate control mesocosm. [D] picture showing biofilm-colonized substrate. [E] Water sampling location in the mesocosms.

Figure S2: Histogram of filter pore sizes previously used in the eDNA literature as reviewed by Takahashi et al. (2023). Filter sizes used herein (.45, 1 and 10 μm) encompass the orders of magnitude found in the literature and some of the most popular pore sizes. Note that while we omitted 0.22 μm in this study (the second most popular filter pore size), we have used it as a fourth filter in a previous study (Brandão-Dias et al., 2023). There, we found that very little eDNA makes it past the 0.45 μm filter in sequential filtration. Therefore, we chose to not use it for this subsequent experiment.

Figure S3: Target eDNA copies by particle size and molecule length in the eDNA source water. Value plotted is the average across four buckets, and error bars are standard error.

Figure S4: Effect of treatments on eDNA removal. [A] Removal rates by treatment (x axis), filter size (panels) and amplicon size (color). [B] Transformed ratio of amplicon removal rates by treatment (x axis) and filter size (panels). Value indicates whether the bigger molecules are removed faster (ratio > 0) or the smaller molecules are removed faster (ratio < 0). Error bars are standard error. ONS = Open no substrate; SNS = Shaded no substrate; OSB = Open substrate; SSB = Shaded substrate; OBF = Open biofilm; SBF = Shaded biofilm.

Figure S5: Change in proportion of eDNA molecule length over time across filter size and treatment. The shaded area represents the 95% confidence interval, and dots show the actual data. ONS = Open no substrate; SNS = Shaded no substrate; OSB = Open substrate; SSB = Shaded substrate; OBF = Open biofilm; SBF = Shaded biofilm.

Figure S6: Stacked area plot of the change of eDNA particle sizes over time for longer molecules. [A] Raw copies by particle size over time, and [B] proportion of each particle size over time. ONS = Open no substrate; SNS = Shaded no substrate; OSB = Open substrate; SSB = Shaded substrate; OBF = Open biofilm; SBF = Shaded biofilm.

Figure S7: Stacked area plot of the change of eDNA particle sizes over time for shorter molecules. [A] Raw copies by particle size over time, and [B] proportion of each particle size over time ONS = Open no substrate; SNS = Shaded no substrate; OSB = Open substrate; SSB = Shaded substrate; OBF = Open biofilm; SBF = Shaded biofilm.